

COMPREHENSIVE MACHINE LEARNING ANALYSIS OF MULTIDOMAIN SPEECH FEATURES FOR DETECTING COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENT

Josep Blazquez-Folch¹, Berta Calm-Salvans¹, Fernando García-Gutiérrez^{1,2}, Nathalia Muñoz¹, Yahveth Cantero-Fortiz^{1,3}, Montserrat Alegret^{1,3}, Agustín Ruiz^{1,3}, Mercè Boada^{1,3}, Marta Marquíé^{1,3}, and Sergi Valero^{1,3}

¹Ace Alzheimer Center Barcelona - Universitat Internacional de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain

²Department of Computer Architecture and Automation, Universidad Complutense, Madrid, Spain

³Networking Research Center on Neurodegenerative Diseases (CIBERNED), Instituto de Salud Carlos III, Madrid, Spain

Background: Developing new accessible strategies for the early detection and remote monitoring of Alzheimer's disease (AD) is becoming an essential aspect of clinical management. Automated speech analysis is one of the most promising approaches for predicting the onset of cognitive impairment. However, current research remains limited by small cohorts and single-domain speech features.

Methods: Since 2022, all patients evaluated at the Memory Unit from Ace Alzheimer Center Barcelona were invited to complete a digital speech protocol (~3 min) that included describing The Cookie Theft Picture, a semantic verbal fluency (SVF) test, and a description of a personal experience. Multidomain speech features were extracted from recordings, including acoustic (n=1203), lexical (n=42), semantic (n=165), syntactic (n=12), and sentiment (n=9) features. These features were used to discriminate among three diagnosis groups: Subjective Cognitive Decline (SCD), Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI), and dementia. Additionally, the speech feature set was used to predict a cognitive composite based on different tests included in a comprehensive neuropsychological battery. Finally, the SHAP framework revealed the most significant features contributing to the Machine Learning (ML) model's performance.

Results: The study included 2320 participants (mean age 75.8, 65.3% female, mean MMSE score=25.2): 249 with SCD, 1209 with MCI, 682 with AD dementia, and 180 with non-AD dementia. Discrimination analysis between pairs of diagnostic groups showed: SCD vs ADD (Sen.=0.92, Spe.=0.96, AUC=0.98), SCD vs MCI (Sen.=0.81, Spe.=0.82, AUC=0.82), MCI vs ADD (Sen.=0.75, Spe.=0.67, AUC=0.76), and SCD vs Cognitively impaired (CI) (Sen.=0.83, Spe.=0.92, AUC=0.88). The speech model demonstrated the strongest performance in predicting the executive composite (correlation 0.82), followed by the memory (0.74) and visuospatial (0.73) composites. The most significant features on the ML model were the number of unique animals and the word frequencies on the SVF test.

Conclusion: This study demonstrates the effectiveness of automated speech analysis in distinguishing between different stages of cognitive impairment. Our results also show a strong correlation of speech features with neuropsychological functions, further supporting the validity of this approach. These findings highlight the potential of speech-based biomarkers as a low cost, non-invasive and easy applicable tool for early detection and remote monitoring of cognitive decline.